

Chemotherapy-Induced Cognitive Impairment: Understanding Through Mangiferin-Mediated Sirtuin Modulation

Jannapu Reddy Shireesha¹, Harish Kumar.B¹, Srinivas Mutalik², K. Sreedhara Ranganath Pai¹,
Nandakumar.K^{1*}

¹*Department of Pharmacology, Manipal College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal-576104, Karnataka, India.*

²*Department of Pharmaceutics, Manipal College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal-576104, Karnataka, India.*

Corresponding Author: Nandakumar.K

Abstract:

Chemobrain, often referred to as chemotherapy-induced cognitive impairment (CICI), is one of the side effects of chemotherapy that long-term breast cancer survivors often experience. The main cause of this illness is thought to be the peripherally and centrally elevated levels of inflammatory cytokines and free oxygen radicals. An essential function of SIRT1, an extremely conserved evolutionary regulator, is to shield living beings from oxidative damage. Notably, the brain's hippocampus regions—a crucial anatomical region intimately linked to memory and learning in the central nervous system—express elevated levels of SIRT1. This association implies that SIRT1 is involved in the control of different forms of cognitive impairment. Consequently, by lowering oxidative stress markers in the brain, regulating SIRT1 activity may be able to lessen CICI. Molecular docking of mangiferin and other phytochemicals that have been identified as human SIRT1 protein activators is the focus of the current investigation. The phytochemical that showed the highest docking score in comparison to the others is then used in molecular dynamics simulations. The investigations consist of multiple essential phases, such as the selection of proteins, production of proteins and ligands, creation of receptor grids, docking of ligands, computation of binding free energy, and molecular dynamic simulation through the use of Maestro version 12.1 from Schrodinger, LLC.

Keywords: Mangiferin, in-silico, SIRT1, Chemotherapy induced cognitive impairment (CICI).

1.INTRODUCTION

Chemotherapy-induced cognitive impairment (CICI), also known as "chemo fog," "chemobrain," or "cognitive disorder due to chemotherapy," is a known side effect experienced by people both prior to and during cancer chemotherapy treatments [1]. The rate of occurrence of this effect in cancer survivors highlights the importance of its diagnosis. It was affecting both short- and long-term quality of life (QOL) [2]. It includes symptoms like lack of focus, decline in memory, difficulty in multitasking, and memorising familiar terms [3], Chemobrain

received more attention due to its impact on 75% of patients taking chemotherapy [4]. Mangiferin (MGF), a naturally occurring C-glucosyl xanthone that is mostly found in different portions of *Mangifera indica*, has become more well-known in this regard [5]. MGF exhibits potential antagonistic action against inflammatory, anxiety, depressive, and noteworthy for its neuroprotective activities. It is chemically called as 1,3,6,7-tetrahydroxy xanthone-C2- β -D-glucoside with anti-oxidant activity [6] is emphasized, for its protection study observed in rodent investigations. MGF may access as a protective barrier for the central nervous system, guarding against oxidative stress, mitochondrial malfunction, and apoptosis from its in-vitro and in-vivo examinations. Based on its investigations it may also enhance memory and cognition [7], promoting MGF as a potential therapeutic agent for neurodegenerative diseases. In light of these properties this study is aimed to investigate Mangiferin neuroprotective benefits against chemobrain.

SIRT1, is a vital component in this scenario and it is a class III histone deacetylase that is NAD⁺-dependent protein [8]. It is present in the prefrontal cortex, basal ganglia, and hippocampal of brain regions highlights its purpose in regulating oxidative stress, inflammation, and ageing. It plays a vital role in physiological processes like DNA repair, metabolism, stress response, and apoptosis [9].

SIRT1 has a structure containing the following different areas within its 747 amino acid sequence: the N-terminal region (1-180 amino acids), the catalytic site (244-512 amino acids), the allosteric site (195-240 amino acids), and the C-terminal portion (513-747 amino acids). The nucleotide bond along with NAD⁺ are present in 261-280, 345-348, 440-442 and 465-467; the amino acids having metal bond are 371, 374, 395 and 398; the amino acids at deacetylase area are 244-498; and the sirtuin-activating compounds (STACs) activating area are at amino acids 195-243 and Glu230. The activation site of SIRT1 is allosteric region used in the treatment of metabolic damages like diabetics and anti-aging [10].

Considering these aspects, this study aims to explore mangiferin's potential as a neuroprotective agent against chemotherapy-induced cognitive impairment, with a particular focus on modulating SIRT1 activity as a potential underlying mechanism through computational methods.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Computational Modelling

We conducted computational modelling studies involving human SIRT1 protein and selected phytochemicals, including Mangiferin, on an HP desktop system with a Linux Ubuntu 18.04.1 LTS platform. The system specifications include an Intel Haswell graphics card, 8 GB RAM, and an Intel Core i3-4160 processor. Maestro version 12.1 from Schrodinger, LLC was employed for these simulations. The investigative processes encompassed protein selection, preparation, ligand preparation, receptor grid creation, ligand docking, binding free-energy calculation, and molecular dynamic simulation.

1. *Protein Selection and Preparation:*

To comprehend the binding patterns of Mangiferin, quinidine, mulberrin, and gartanin with SIRT1, we employed the crystal structure of SIRT1 protein, designated as 4ZZJ. This structure comprises a SIRT1/activator/substrate complex, featuring a heterodimeric open conformation bound to a peptide substrate derived from p53 (chain B), along with small molecule sirtuin activating compound 4TQ and non-hydrolysable NAD⁺ analogue carba NAD (chain A), resolved to 2.74 Å. The crystal structure was retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank, reviewed, modified, and minimized through the protein preparation wizard tool. The protein underwent preprocessing, encompassing the filling of missing loops and side chains using the Prime tool at PROPKA pH set to 7.4. Essential residues were retained, followed by the addition of hydrogen atoms and the removal of water molecules beyond 5 Å. Subsequent energy minimization utilized the OPLS3e force field to achieve a low-energy state protein at an RMSD of 0.3 Å, employed for subsequent simulation studies.

2. *Ligand Preparation:*

For molecular docking studies involving Mangiferin and other established SIRT1 activators with SIRT1 protein, we utilized LigPrep tool for ligand preparation. We employed the OPLS3e force field and set the pH at 7.4 ± 0.5 to generate possible ionization states.

3. *Receptor Grid Generation:*

The receptor grid was generated by selecting atoms within the binding site of the co-crystallized ligand within the minimized protein. This region was designated for ligand docking and subsequent processing steps.

4. *Molecular Docking:*

Utilizing the generated grid, molecular docking studies were conducted in extra precision (XP) mode using the Glide tool. These studies facilitated the identification of interactions between the ligands and the protein, along with associated dock scores.

5. *Binding Free Energy Calculation:*

We determined the binding free energy of Mangiferin against the SIRT1 protein using the Prime Molecular Mechanics-Generalized Borne Surface Area (MM-GBSA) tool of the Maestro program by using VSGB solvent model and OPLS3e force field.

6. *Molecular Dynamics Simulations:*

Addressing the limitations of grid-based docking methods in simulating biological systems, we employed Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations. Based on parameters such as GLIDE docking score, free binding energy, a medication was chosen for a 20ns MD simulation. The process included system building, minimization, and MD simulation phases. The system model, incorporating a preset SPC solvent under orthorhombic boundary conditions, was subjected to energy minimization using the NPT ensemble until a gradient threshold of 25 kcal/mol/Å was achieved. This was balanced at a temperature of 300 K and a pressure of 1 bar. The MD simulation was subsequently used to examine the minimized ligand-protein complex.

7. Analysis Post MD Simulation:

Following MD simulation, we calculated the Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) of the protein and ligand, alongside an analysis of ligand interactions during the simulation. RMSD, a measure of the average change in displacement of selected atoms in relation to a reference frame, was calculated as per the following equation:

$$RMSD_x = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (r'_i(t_x) - r_i(t_{ref}))^2}$$

The number of atoms in the atom selection is N. The reference time is t_{ref} , and the chosen atoms' location in frame x is r.

8. Virtual Screening of Phytochemicals:

Within this study, we meticulously analysed and elucidated the docking scores and binding interactions of mangiferin and other phytochemicals previously reported as SIRT1 activators in prior studies.

III.RESULTS

A. Molecular docking

We conducted *in-silico* study to explore the modulation of SIRT1 utilizing Schrodinger Maestro software 11.7.011, release 2018-3. Prior research has already reported the SIRT1 activation potential of Quinidine, Mulberrin, and Gartanin, substantiated through a combination of *in silico* and *in-vitro* study results. Our docking studies unveiled critical amino acid residues ILE223 and ILE227 within the allosteric regions. Notably, GLU230, situated in the N-terminal domain, emerged as pivotal for activation by previously reported STACs and a novel class of distinct chemical activators. The results were summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Docking score, binding energy, and interacting residues with 2D representation for SIRT1 (4ZZJ) protein with Mangiferin, quercetin, quinidine, mulberin and gartanin.

Sl. No	Drug	Docking score	Binding energy Kcal/mol	Bonding and Non-bonding interactions	Interaction diagram
1	Mangiferin	-2.29	-21.89	Hydrogen bonding: ASN226, GLU230 Hydrophobic bonds: LEU215, ILE223, ILE227, LEU206 Negative charges: GLU230 Positive charges: THR219, ASN226	

2	Quinidine	-0.712	-26.61	Hydrogen bonds: GLU230 Hydrophobic bonds: ILE223, PRO231, ILE227 Negative charge : GLU230 Positive charges: ASN226, SER229	
3	Mulberin	-1.145	-20.17	Hydrophobic bonds: LEU206, ILE210, PRO211, PRO212, ILE227, ILE223 Positive charges: THR209, THR219, GLN222, ASN226	
4	Gartanin	-0.662	-32.29	Hydrogen bond: ASN226, GLU230 Hydrophobic bond: ILE227, ILE223, LEU220, LEU206, LEU202, PRO211, PRO212, LEU215 Positive charges: THR209, THR219, GLN222, ASN226 Negative charges: GLU230	

Mangiferin exhibited a high docking score in comparison to other phytochemicals with established SIRT1 activation properties via *in-vitro* studies. Additionally, Mangiferin demonstrated robust docking interactions with key amino acid residues: ILE223, ILE227, and GLU230. This observation aligns with the SIRT1 structure (PDB ID 4ZZJ), revealing interactions between Mangiferin and the allosteric region. These interactions were characterized by Hydrophobic bonds at LEU215, ILE223, ILE227, LEU206, along with hydrogen bonding at Asn226 and GLU230.

The active conformation model of SIRT1 includes a STAC complex with the Ac-p53 substrate, highlighting amino acid hydrogen bond interactions involving Glu230 and Arg446. Mangiferin binding was found to augment SIRT1 activity and stabilize deacetylase activity. This effect was achieved through encouraging Substrate Binding Domain (SBD) engagement with the core catalytic region of the substrate. Molecular dynamic studies were performed to investigate the interaction between Mangiferin and the SIRT1 protein.

Table 1 shows the calculated binding free energy from the stimulations of molecular docking for the phytochemicals with SIRT1. The binding energy is between -20.17 Kcal/mol and -32.29 Kcal/mol, the Mangiferin showed the binding energy of -21.89 Kcal/mol like other phytochemical which are proven to be SIRT1 activators.

2. Molecular Dynamics:

The molecular dynamics was conducted for 20 ns to investigate the in-silico study in detail. The RMSD gives the information regarding the binding stability of the complex. Fig. 1 (a) shows the protein deviated from 2 to 8 Å and the ligand Mangiferin show deviation from 2 to 16 Å. We can say that after undergoing conformational changes the Mangiferin have showed interaction with hydrogen, hydrophobic, ionic and water bridge bonds with amino acids Asn226, Ser229, Lys235, Leu206, Ile223, Ile227, Leu205, Thr209, Ile210, Thr219, Gln222, Glu230, Lys233, Lys236, Lys328, Glu458. The ligand is contacting with amino acid Asn 226, Ser 229, Ile227, Ile223 from Fig. 1 (b). From this study we can also say that Mangiferin may also modulate SIRT1. Fig. 1 (c) shows duration of interaction between hydroxyl group on glucoxyl moiety of Mangiferin and Ser229 of SIRT1 was 83 percent and another hydroxy with Asn226 was 87 percent. The hydroxyl group on xanthone moiety of Mangiferin interacted with carbonyl group at 82 percent. The carbonyl group on xanthone moiety of Mangiferin interacted with Asn226 at 37 percent. Notably, the ligand contacts amino acids ASN 226, SER 229, ILE227, and ILE223, akin to 4TQ molecules established as SIRT1 modulators. Collectively, these insights suggest that Mangiferin also holds the potential to modulate SIRT1 activity.

Fig. 1 MD stimulation of Mangiferin and SIRT1 complex (a) Root Mean Square Deviation plot of Mangiferin with SIRT1 (b) The protein-ligand contacts: Interactions of Mangiferin with different amino acid residues of SIRT1 protein (c) The 2D interactions of Mangiferin with SIRT1

IV.DISCUSSION

Chemotherapy-induced cognitive impairment (CICI) is a complex condition characterized by cognitive deficits such as memory problems, reduced attention, concentration difficulties, and impaired multitasking during the chemotherapy treatment. There are numerous mechanisms like oxidative stress, inflammation, and variations in neurotransmitters leading to chemobrain [11].

The SIRT1 acts against the oxidative stress and reactive oxygen species (ROS) are generated by chemotherapy and protects neurons [12]. It decreases the proinflammatory cytokines and fights against inflammation causing memory decline [13]. It helps in repairing DNA and aids mitochondrial activity in the process of maintaining neuronal health [14]. It also helps in modulation of neurotransmitters involved in cognition and enhances neuroplasticity [15]. In addition, it plays significant role in neuronal vitality and cognition through epigenetic mechanism. [16].

Considering these multifaceted roles, manipulating SIRT1 activity holds promise as a therapeutic approach to addressing chemotherapy-induced cognitive dysfunction. By activating SIRT1, it might be possible to enhance cellular resilience against oxidative stress, mitigate inflammation, and promote neuronal survival. Hence, this target (SIRT1) was selected to explore the possibility against CICI. In the current study, we studied the interaction between phyto molecules and SIRT1 protein. Based on the literature evidence and other criteria like (easy availability, cost, easy to isolate and characterise etc) we selected four phytomolecules (viz. quinidine, mangiferin, mulberrin, and gartanin) to study the interaction of these molecules with the SIRT1 protein. Out of the four compounds studied mangiferin showed the highest docking score with more positive interactions on the SIRT1 protein suggesting mangiferin could be a promising SIRT1 modulator. However, further *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* testing are required to confirm this aspect to take it forward as a potential compound against chemotherapy induced cognitive dysfunction.

V.CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our results collectively underscore the potential of SIRT1 modulation as a compelling strategy for addressing chemotherapy-induced cognitive decline. The distinct attributes of Mangiferin, highlighted through its interactions with SIRT1, provide an exciting avenue for exploring interventions against cognitive impairments arising from chemotherapy. These findings lay the foundation for further investigations and validations.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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